

Effects of methanol extracts from *Ophiopogon japonicus* on rice blast fungus

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Previous studies showed that dwarf lilyturf (*Ophiopogon japonicus* Ker-Gawl.) (Izawa 1967, Kishima 1963) contains allelopathic chemicals, which inhibited the germination and initial growth of three weeds—barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli* L.), monochoria (*Monochoria vaginalis* Presl), and smallflower umbrella (*Cyperus difformis* L.) (Lin 2001). This study determined whether methanol extracts of dwarf lilyturf have inhibitory effects on rice blast fungus *Pyricularia grisea*.

Fresh roots and root tubers of dwarf lilyturf plants were washed with distilled water and oven-dried at 50 °C for 48 h. About 100 g of dried samples were cut into 1-cm-long pieces and ground in a juice mixer for 15 min. Eight grams of dry powder were soaked in 80 mL 70% methanol solution at 5 °C for 24 h and filtered through No. 2 filter paper (Toyo Roshi Kaisha Ltd., Japan). The supernatant was sufficiently concentrated and evaporated to a solid state through a rotary vacuum evaporator (Tokyo Rikakikai Co., Ltd., Japan) and dissolved in 10 mL sterile distilled water used as original solution. Then, 1/2, 1/4, and 1/8 dilutions were prepared. One mL each of these doses was blended with 9 mL of 0.8% potato dextrose agar (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd., Japan) culture solution and placed in a 9-cm petri dish to give a final concentration of 1/10, 1/20, 1/40, and 1/80 of the origi-

nal solution. The 0.01 mg spores of two isolates of *P. grisea* (MAFF305480 and MAFF101002), which mainly occur in Miyazaki Prefecture, southern Japan, were inoculated in the center of the petri dish. The colony diameters of the mycelial plugs were measured 10 d after being kept in a growth chamber with 4,000 lux artificial light (0700–1900) at –25 °C. The control was the same as the treatments, except that distilled water was used instead of an extract. No fungal contamination was observed during the whole experiment. Five treatments, including the control, were arranged in a completely randomized design with three replications. Comparisons of all treatments were made at the 0.05 probability level using the least significant difference method. Inhibitory percentage was calculated using the formula [(control value – treatment value)/control value] × 100.

The results shown in Figures 1 and 2 indicate that methanol extracts from dried powder of dwarf lilyturf inhibited the mycelial growth of the two isolates of *P. grisea*. In particular, the extract with 1/10 concentration completely inhibited mycelial growth of both MAFF305480 and MAFF101002, whereas the 1/20 concentration inhibited mycelial growth of MAFF305480 and MAFF101002 by 100% and 81%, respectively. The results suggest that the dwarf lilyturf plants have inhibitory potential and could be

used as a biological fungicide to control rice blast. We have identified and isolated six allelopathic chemicals from methanol extracts of dwarf lilyturf plants (unpubl. data): *o*-hydroxybenzoic acid; 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzoic acid; 4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxy benzoic acid; 3,5-dimethoxy-4-hydroxycinnamic acid; syringaldehyde; and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid. We plan to evaluate the efficacy of these extracts in controlling rice blast in the field.

Fig. 1. Effects of methanol extracts from dwarf lilyturf on colony diameter of inoculated *P. grisea* in vitro. (Numbers in parentheses indicate inhibitory percentage; different letters indicate significant differences at 5% between treatments within the same isolate.)

Fig. 2. Effects of methanol extracts from dwarf lilyturf plants on mycelial growth of *P. grisea*.

References

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Fingerprinting the rice isolates of *R. solani* Kuhn using RAPD markers

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The genetic differences underlying *Rhizoctonia solani* populations provide a useful means for examining the nature and spread of the population within the rice system. So far, no attempt has been made to define variability in relation to spatial distribution and no information is available on the amount of variability in *R. solani* within the field. Many anastomosis groups are subdivided on the basis of the cultural, virulence, molecular, biochemical, immunological, and other characteristics into intraspecific groups (ISGs) (Ogoshi 1987). The most convincing validation of AG and ISG concepts has come from molecular systematic studies (Vilgalys and Cubeta 1994). Our study was undertaken to (1) analyze the interfield variability within 46 Indian rice isolates of *R. solani* collected from two fields, one each at Seola-Kala, Dehradun District (hilly region, 24 isolates), and Nagina, Bijnora District (plain region, 22 isolates), for cultural and morphological characteristics, aggressiveness, anastomosis behavior, nuclear staining, and molecular characterization by RAPD analysis; (2) assess the agreement among five methods in differentiating the isolates; and

(3) study the extent and possible factors responsible for intrafield variability in rice. This is the first attempt to define intrafield variability among *R. solani* isolates that cause sheath blight in rice.

Of 22 primers that were screened, the following eight were selected for amplifying DNA of all the isolates: T11 = 5'-GTCCATTCAGTCGGTGCT-3'; T13 = 5'-G A A T G C C T T C C A A G C C G G T-3'; C15 = 5'-G G T G C C A C G A G T A A T C-3'; G16 = 5'-C C A G T C T T C G T A G A G A A T C G-3'; T19 = 5'-G T A A A C G A C G G C C A G T-3'; C20 = 5'-A T G G A T C C G C-3'; G21 = 5'-G A G T A C G T G C T C G C T C G A T G-3'; and C22 = 5'-T G G G T C G A G G G G T T C-3'. Amplified polymerase chain reaction products were separated on agarose gel (Fig. 1). A dendrogram was constructed using Jaccard's similarity coefficient and UPGMA clustering using NTSYS-PC version 2.11a (Rohlf 2000). The cut-off point to decide the number of clusters was determined using canonical discriminant function analysis by SPSS Software Version 10.

All isolates were multinucleate and shared typical characteristics with *R. solani*. They exhib-

ited varying degrees of virulence on Pusa Basmati 1 and, on the basis of the disease severity (lesion length), could be classified as highly virulent (2), moderately virulent (7), less virulent (33), and avirulent (40). All isolates gave two (incompatible fusion) or three types of anastomosis reaction (compatible fusion) with the tester isolate of *R. solani* (N15) belonging to AG-1 IA.

The dendrogram, constructed using 88 polymorphic bands obtained with eight primers and 41 isolates, was divided into seven clusters at 0.125 similarity level (Fig. 2). No amplification was obtained with isolates N3, D5, D22, D23, and D24. The isolates N18 (crushed and mycelial aggregate-type sclerotia) and N16 (macro sclerotia) were present independently at the 12.5% similarity level. Among isolates of cluster 1 (N1, N9, N13, N14, N15, N20, N21, N22, and D12), similarity values ranged from 13.7% to 32.5%, whereas, among isolates of cluster 2 (D1, D3, D6, D7, D10, D11, D15, D16, D17, D18, D19, D20, and N17), cluster 3 (N8, N19, D2, and D13), cluster 4 (N6, N11, and N12), cluster 5 (D9, D14, and D21), cluster 6 (N2, D4, and D8), and cluster 7